

PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER

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Abstract. *On the basis of theoretical data, the article systematically analyzes the psychological and pedagogical aspects of the problem of pedagogical competence of specialists in physical culture.*

Key words: *physical education, specialist, knowledge, skills, competence, basic competences, teacher, pedagogical competence.*

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ СОВРЕМЕННОГО УЧИТЕЛЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ВОСПИТАНИЯ

Аннотация. *На основе теоретических данных в статье системно анализируются психолого-педагогические аспекты проблемы педагогической компетентности специалистов физической культуры.*

Ключевые слова: *физическое воспитание, специалист, знания, умения, компетентность, базовые компетенции, учитель, педагогическая компетентность.*

INTRODUCTION

In our democratic society, based on the conditions of today's market relations, the suitability of each specialist for a position is measured by how much he meets the totality of various requirements for the owner of this job or profession. Several educational concepts related to the study of professional competencies in a number of countries of the world and the practical application of the results of such a study in order to develop a basis for calculating the level of suitability of the applicant in place of an existing job or service in subsequent years have been created.

In these concepts, the main goal of modern education is to meet the current (prospective) needs of the individual, society and the state, a versatile person who is able to educate and improve himself in social and (or) labor activity, capable of social activity. adaptive formation of a person. Only a teacher who thinks independently and broadly, predicts the future results of his activity and appropriately systematically models the educational process, is the key to achieving this goal. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, as in all developed countries, in the modern, rapidly changing globalized world, the need for teachers with high competence and creative thinking, capable of educating a competent and competitive personality, has sharply increased.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The reason is that the above goal can only be achieved by truly pedagogically literate, that is, independent and (or) able to think creatively and critically outside the "boundaries", able to make reliable decisions in any problem situation, competently solve pedagogical problems. the tasks assigned to him can be solved only by teachers who are able to fully express themselves professionally (Hard Skills) and personally (Soft Skills).

Thus, the formation of professional and (or) pedagogical competence of a modern teacher is one of the urgent problems and is understood as a set of professional and (or) personal qualities necessary for the organization of successful pedagogical activity. And the importance of personal competencies is extremely high. The word "competence" comes from the Latin word

"competere", which means "capable", "corresponding". "Competence" means a person's awareness in a particular area, the level of knowledge in this area.

In modern pedagogy and psychology, there is no single approach to defining the concept of professional competence of a teacher. As a reason for this, it is recognized that "competence" is one of the terms that has not yet been sufficiently studied in educational psychology, and in many cases it is intuitively used to express a sufficient level of competence and professionalism (L.M. Mitina, 2012).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Also, the analysis of scientific sources shows that the concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in non-standard situations, unexpected situations, enters into communication, approaches relations with opponents in a new way, performs ambiguous tasks, is conflicted" means "possession of an action plan". movement in the use of information, consistently developing and complex processes" (N. Muslimov et al., 2015).

The analysis of scientific literature showed that researchers use different approaches to the definition of professional competence. In particular, European and American researchers studied the practical aspects of professional competence, i.e. a complex of knowledge, skills and abilities that affect the environment (I. Borg, M. Müller, T. Staufenbiel), serving for the successful completion of the task (M. Perlmutter, M. Kaplan, L. Nyquist); was studied as a provider of specific actions in the structure of activity (G. Schroeder, M. Forverg), as an applicator of practical methods to cognitive processes (S.P. Dyrstra, S. Dollinger) (O.S. Kiseleva, 2008).

According to the literature, competence is a measurement of the changing mood and behavior of people, which is the basis of an effective workflow (O.E. Khaitov, 2008). Thus, the effectiveness of the work process of the future teacher of physical culture comes from the indicator of his effective behavior.

In pedagogical research, the professional competence of a modern teacher is studied in seven types (N.A. Muslimov, 2005). In particular, global competence; sociocultural competence; social competence; the ability to receive information; communicative competence; academic competence; types of competence related to practical activities. This division serves as an important criterion in studying the level of pedagogical competence of a physical education teacher.

Thus, pedagogical competence is a combination of professional and personal qualities that ensure the implementation of these competencies (A.S. Belkin, V.V. Nesterov, 2003). At the same time, the structure of pedagogical competence is as follows: although it is expressed through cognitive (professional and pedagogical erudition) and psychological (emotional and emotional culture, communication with students, the formation of motives and the development of students' abilities) competencies, constructive and (or) organizational role (managerial) competencies remains practically unexplored.

In our opinion, constructive competence includes the ability to design lesson / coaching activities, extracurricular activities, assignments and (or) tasks of various levels, independent work of students, communication, etc. It becomes important to plan and model future pedagogical activity (physical education classes) (amateur activities and students, the choice and composition of the content, means, methods, forms of organization of educational activities, the

allocation of stages of activity and setting goals). Also, the organizational (managerial) competence of a physical education teacher includes the content of the educational process, the ability to organize and coordinate the physical education activities of students and the behavior of the teacher. For example, this competence is clearly manifested in the correct presentation of educational material in the classroom, setting clear tasks for students, disclosing the content of their implementation, showing and explaining physical exercises, and helping students in their implementation. In this case, the management of students means the correct direction of their attention, the exact implementation of the formation and reformation, preparation for motor activity, the correct use of exercises for their intended purpose, the correct distribution of physical activity.

CONCLUSION

In general, if we consider a complex theoretical analysis, then, first of all, the success of the implementation of pedagogical activity depends on the extent to which the teacher of physical culture has mastered the necessary professional competencies. Secondly, based on the areas of professional activity, the competence-based approach is of particular importance in revealing the originality of the special pedagogical competence of a physical education teacher - cognitive, health-improving, communicative, subject-instrumental, creative competencies.

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